

CONCEPTUAL ISSUES OF THE CONCEPTS OF PROSOCIAL BEHAVIOR AND ALTRUISM**Salamova A.***Teacher of the Department of General Sciences of ADPU Sheki branch*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169140>**Abstract**

Socialization is an event that we need at every stage of life and that ensures that people live together. The level of development of the social structure is provided by behaviors that will improve the society. Prosocial to children at an early age teaching behavior helps them behave more healthily in society when they become adults and contributes to the well-being of society.

Psychology, which examines people's emotions, thoughts and behaviors, also examines human prosocial behavior from various aspects.

Research shows that instead of seeking happiness in external pleasures, it is more satisfying to seek it in activities that give inner meaning to an individual's life, such as personal growth, close relationships, and social assistance. Altruistic behaviors are thought to give people value and meaning in their lives and improve the quality of their moods in today's hostile societies by changing the way they view people other than themselves. Prosocial behaviors have been shown to have benefits for self-esteem, life satisfaction, and general mental health.

Keywords: social behavior, prosocial behavior, altruism, helping behavior, social reciprocity, social responsibility, social justice, empathy, mental health

The actuality of the subject. "A person is constantly from the moment of birth to the end of his life with the external environment connected. Therefore, he is considered a social being, he lives in the society and can influence the society in which he lives, and the society can also influence him. Most of the behaviors are shaped by the influence of social environment. After death, a person tries to send a message to people and create a positive image by creating works bearing his name or charitable institutions in order to be well remembered and to make a name. The rules of social behavior are considered unwritten laws of human relations, and people try to adapt their behavior, attitudes, and actions to these unwritten rules in their social life. A person living in society knows that behavior that does not take into account social expectations will not be accepted. If these boundaries are not met, there is no formal punishment other than being exposed to a more or less societal reaction. But when these rules are followed, an individual makes a difference both in his personal life and in his work life. He becomes someone who is loved, respected and valuable" [3, p. 5]. Thus, social behavior is a social activity aimed at ensuring the adaptation of an individual to social systems, nature and culture.

In modern psychology, topics and problems related to people's social relations remain relevant. In this article, the main goal is to examine the motives and goals of people helping and helping each other in social relations, and the factors that determine the behavior of mutual help. Including altruism and its conceptual issues in terms of prosocial behaviors.

The concept of prosocial behavior was recorded by the psychologist and researcher Daniel Batson as an antonym of the antisocial concept. First of all, it should be noted that in social psychology textbooks and psychological dictionaries, prosocial behavior is defined as a behavior that is beneficial to other people. In other words, the intention and purpose of the help or benefit given to someone else is not important here.

This can be determined both by a person's selfish purpose (for example, to win the sympathy of others, the expectation of returning the help he has done in the future, etc.), and by altruistic purposes for the benefit of others, without thinking about his own benefit, even if it is to his own detriment. Taking into account that prosocial behavior includes a wider scope, any act of helping, the present study aims to determine the socio-psychological factors that motivate people to prosocial behavior.

Prosocial behavior is positive social behavior or the intention to benefit others. It is a set of social behaviors that benefit other people or society as a whole, such as helping, sharing, donating, cooperating, and volunteering. In addition, behaviors such as following rules or conforming to social expectations are also considered pro-social behaviors. There are individual and social influences that will influence a person's prosocial behavior. In individual behavior, a person can act according to the behavior of people around him or he can do this action with factors such as protecting or increasing his reputation.

Individuals may be oriented toward prosocial behavior based on learning and socialization during childhood. Helping skills and the habit of helping others are acquired socially. As the child understands why the skills he possesses should be used to help the people around him, his motivation to help increases accordingly. These behaviors of individuals who behave in accordance with the norms of social responsibility and social reciprocity during childhood are reinforced by adults and become a habit. When individuals engage in these types of behaviors, they maintain positive perceptions of themselves and their thoughts and meet their needs.

There are many factors and motivations that mediate the growth and spread of prosocial behaviors. These factors can be distinguished as individual and situational factors. For example, empathy is a powerful motivator for engaging in prosocial behavior. In addition, the norm of reciprocity, altruism,

responsibility and guilt, mood and emotions are also affected. This can be achieved through motivations such as caring for the well-being of others.

Prosocial behavior factors include:

The audience effect. The effect of this effect is that in a crisis, as the number of people who witness the situation increases, the likelihood that the person in need of help will receive help decreases. For example, when a person falls down in a crowded street, most people will simply walk past the fallen person without attempting to help. The pattern can also be adapted to more urgent situations, such as a traffic accident or natural disaster. One explanation for this effect, according to the decision model, is that when individuals make decisions, they evaluate whether the current situation requires their help, whether they have a duty to help, and how they should help. The decision model suggests the following 5 elements necessary for helping or intervention behavior to occur:

- ✓ situational awareness;
- ✓ interpretation of the witnessed situation by a person as an emergency;
- ✓ creating a sense of responsibility in the individual;
- ✓ belief that the individual has the skills to be successful in helping;
- ✓ the individual reaching a conscious decision to help.

In addition to the five items, the number of people who witnessed the help-seeking situation also influences a person's decision to help. As the number of witnesses increases, so does the likelihood that they will help, as everyone's perceived personal responsibility decreases. This situation is called diffusion of responsibility. The sense of responsibility is divided by the number of people who witnessed the event, and the amount of responsibility that falls on one person decreases.

People are more likely to help people in a social group or group than they are to help people outside of that group. When an individual is accepted as a member of a group with a shared sense of identity, a sense of affinity for that person and a sense of responsibility for both the situation that creates the need for help and the general social well-being of the person in question will increase. Thus, the helper is able to devote more time and energy to the helping behavior and his motivation to engage in prosocial behavior increases. Also, social isolation reduces the likelihood of prosocial behavior. One does not want to devote one's energy and time to group members who exclude one.

Emotional awakening. Another example of individual factors of positive social behavior is emotional arousal, empathy and altruism. This type of empathy is feelings of sensitivity, compassion and sympathy. According to another model of empathy and altruism, feeling empathy for someone in need increases the likelihood of prosocial behavior. For example, an individual who has sensitivity and compassion for children, when he sees a child in a difficult situation on the street, he will empathize and help the child in need more. It was noted that this situation increases the positive mood of the individual.

It has been established that emotional arousal is not only positive, but also negative moods such as guilt and fear lead to positive social behavior.

The observation effect. Social determinants of prosocial behavior include the observability effect as an example. People generally engage in more prosocial behaviors in public spaces than in their private spaces when they are in society. This effect increases individuals' perception of status and the likelihood that they will be more valued and accepted by others who engage in positive social behavior. In addition, a study on the observation effect notes that images containing human eyes activate an involuntary neural gaze detection mechanism in humans that increases social behavior.

Prosocial behaviors, in their purest form, arise from altruism, a selfless interest in helping another person. Empathy with an individual in need or a close relationship between the person performing the behavior and the person affected by the behavior are the conditions in which altruism is most likely to emerge. However, many seemingly altruistic prosocial behaviors are underpinned by the norm of reciprocity, that is, the obligation to do good in return. People feel guilty when they don't reciprocate kindness, and they can get angry when someone doesn't reciprocate kindness. Prosocial behaviors may be driven by the expectation that one's reputation as a social individual will be heard in the social environment and thus benefit long-term interactions. Such an expectation, in particular, motivates the socially visible helping behavior of selfish individuals.

Feeling guilty is also considered a motivational element of prosocial behavior. When the harm caused by one person to another person is compensated by a third party, the guilt feelings, restorative intentions and prosocial behavior of the person causing the harm are greatly reduced. For this reason, it is suggested that the feeling of guilt may be related to some form of reparation for the harm caused, rather than the need for social behavior.

Engaging in prosocial behavior can be beneficial in improving individuals' mood and mental health. Cultivating positive emotions such as gratitude can also facilitate prosocial behavior. Gratitude increases helping behavior even when the cost of helping someone in need is high. It has also been found that gratitude can increase not only close social ties, but also help to strangers.

It is known that people also struggle with psychological problems and dissatisfaction with life. It is thought that one of the important reasons for this situation is the concept of life created by ignoring psychological needs in order to be happy by running after dreams and desires. When individuals focus only on their own wants and needs, they become narcissistic and ignore the people around them and their needs. Since social relations in selfish societies are generally driven by self-interest, interpersonal relations weaken and society actually becomes lonely. However, it has been observed that people in this social structure focused on self-satisfaction become more unhappy over time because the elements of internal satisfaction that

will provide psychological satisfaction are not paid attention to.

"It is understood that the transformation of the passions of individuals in these societies into more constructive directions than their own is one of the most important elements for getting rid of selfishness and dissatisfaction. For this reason, it is considered important to support the selfless behavior and personal goals of today's young people who are raising their own generation, such as implementing voluntary projects and participating in social assistance. Thus, the social relations established by young people gain quality and support them to see the meaning of life" [6, p. 207].

The concept of altruism, which Auguste Comte (19th century) first defined as "the tendency or desire to live for others", is defined as positive social (prosocial) behavior or useful behavior. A widely used definition of altruism is given by Batson and Shaw (1991) as follows; "it is a state of motivation aimed at improving the well-being of another". Basically, altruism involves various behaviors performed by an individual or group to ensure the well-being or enhance the well-being of others.

Altruism is a Latin word meaning "for another". Therefore, altruism is based on giving preference to people other than oneself. "The meaning of the concept of altruism has been discussed in a similar way in different sciences. The concept of altruism is "a moral attitude and view that accepts self-sacrifice for the well-being of others as a principle, regardless of personal benefit", "a view that turns the well-being of others into a principle of living and action", "a condition for the moral and cultural development of humanity", "instead of selfishness and self-love, others a state of directed love", "a state of readiness to give up one's own interests", "to help others for the good of others and for unselfish purposes" [1, p. 349]. Apparently, fields such as education, philosophy, psychology, and sociology include altruistic behavior in their vocabulary and use it as the opposite of selfishness.

The concept of altruism has been translated in some studies as "being useful", in others as "thinking of others", and in others as "being selfless". However, although altruism means "thinking about another," it refers to a different phenomenon than benevolence and altruism. However, there is a subtle difference between altruism and altruism. While altruism is more about thinking of one another, altruism is sacrificing oneself under pressure from the environment. For this reason, altruism can be defined as a helping behavior that favors another.

"Behavior that can be beneficial to another person or a group of people and that a person exhibits voluntarily and without pressure" is included in the scope of pro-social behavior.

"Batson and Shaw altruism is a motivation in which the primary goal is to increase the welfare of another explains the situation and feel good about those who help altruistic behaviors according to them is to ensure that the person who shows altruistic behavior is actually the one in front of him he should aim for his good. And Krebs, altruism is the person's own good for

another expressed as his desire to sacrifice his well-being" [4, p. 111].

All positive behavior of people towards other beings can be considered as pro-social behavior. Helping behavior is a type of prosocial behavior and includes all mutual or unilateral helping activities of individuals. If the help is one-sided rather than mutual, and the helper acts with the needs of the other in the foreground, this is called altruistic behavior.

Altruism is a helping behavior that also aims to benefit someone or protect them from possible harm. Altruistic behavior is voluntary behavior. In other words, an individual willingly helps someone in need and expects nothing but satisfaction in doing good to a person in need. Accordingly, the measure of whether a behavior is altruistic depends on the intention of the helper. People are willing to help even strangers in need. However, we are more willing to help people we know.

Theories of altruistic behavior. There are ideas from evolutionary, cultural, and learning approaches that explain helping others willingly and without expecting anything in return.

The evolutionary approach describes helping behavior in animals and humans as a genetic trait that is passed down from generation to generation. Organisms with altruistic behavior help their offspring with whom they share their genes and ensure that their genes are inherited. However, the idea that helping behavior is a genetic trait passed from person to person is controversial. It is argued that mankind's instinct to perpetuate its offspring may not be the primary motivation in every case.

According to the cultural approach, social values form the basis of altruistic behavior. Positive social behaviors have become part of social norms because they are beneficial to individuals. Among the cultural norms with which an individual grows up, three have been found to be associated with helping behavior: social responsibility, reciprocity, and social justice. Social responsibility is a norm that tells us to help people who need our help. Reciprocity tells us to help those who help. Social justice emphasizes the principle of equal reward for equal work. A sense of equality can also be seen as a result of doing good to others.

Getting help from someone while doing something increases our tendency to help them when they need it. The learning approach to helping behavior assumes that it is learned during the socialization process.

Stages of altruistic behavior decision making. The process of deciding to help is completed in four steps:

The first step is to recognize the problem that needs help. At the end of this perception, it is decided whether help is needed. "When deciding whether an incident requires assistance or not, the presence of five indicators is taken into account:

- ✓ the event is sudden and unexpected;
- ✓ there is a clear threat of harm to the victim;
- ✓ if no intervention is made, the harm to the victim will increase;

- ✓ the victim's desperation and need for help is clear;
- ✓ it is possible to intervene that will give results" [5, p.114].

The second step, is to take personal responsibility. We tend to take responsibility for helping relatives more than strangers. Furthermore, when we have the skills required to help, our responsibility to help increases.

The third step, is to consider what the benefits and costs of liability would be. The result should be worth the effort. Along with the benefits and costs of aid, outcomes are also considered. For example, not helping someone who needs help can make a person feel guilty. On the other hand, if you don't help when you should, they won't think well of you if seen by others.

The fourth step, is to decide on the form of aid and take action. How should we intervene in the situation we are facing? What can be done to make the results healthier and more positive? This urgency can often lead to extremely negative situations when trying to do good.

Reasons for differences in altruistic behavior among people.

Emotional state and altruistic behavior.

Mood and social behavior are two closely related phenomena. People often experience the "feel-good-behave-good" phenomenon. When people feel happy and joyful, they are more willing to help others. The existence of a relationship between positive mood and helping has been proven by research. Helping helps maintain a positive emotional state. Good emotions make us think more positively. On the other hand, it reduces altruistic behavior when the help given is thought to disrupt positive emotions in the person. In short, people who experience positive emotional states want to maintain this state. Research findings on the effects of people's negative emotions on helping behavior are inconsistent. Feeling bad can reduce a person's ability to help others. On the other hand, if helping someone else will relieve or alleviate pessimism in the person, it may motivate the person to help. Helping others to get rid of a negative emotional state does not always work. But it can be said that helping others generally makes people feel good.

Helping motives: empathy and bad feeling. The emotions that motivate people to help without expecting anything in return have also been explored. Seeing someone in a difficult and helpless situation evokes strong emotions in a person. One of them is feeling bad. Feeling bad is an emotional response to negative events experienced by others. Emotional reactions such as shock, anxiety, helplessness that a person feels in front of a situation he witnesses are bad feelings.

"C. Daniel Batson (1991) is the strongest proponent of the idea that people often help purely out of the goodness of their hearts. Batson acknowledges that people sometimes help others for selfish reasons, such as to relieve their own distress at seeing another person suffer. But he also argues that people's motives are sometimes purely altruistic, in that their only goal is to help the other person, even if doing so involves some

cost to them. Pure altruism is likely to come into play, he maintains, when we feel empathy for the person in need of help, putting ourselves in the shoes of another person and experiencing events and emotions the way that person experiences them" [2, p. 349-350]. So, empathy is the ability of a person to understand the feelings of another person by putting himself in another person's place and making the other person feel it. Empathy occurs when attention is focused on a person's feelings and thoughts. When you feel bad, you experience feelings of fear, anxiety, and reluctance. Again, feeling bad motivates people to reduce their anxiety. We do this by helping people in need. However, there is no necessary relationship between feeling bad and helping behavior. Some people can feel good by ignoring the negativity around them and moving away from them. In empathy, it is important to try to understand the other person. It causes empathy and compassion and motivates us to help. Her goal is to help others feel good about themselves. Therefore, empathy is an altruistic behavior. We can empathize more with people who are similar to us. We empathize more with people who are struggling due to uncontrollable circumstances or causes beyond their control. Empathy can also be increased by paying attention to the objective conditions that created the situation. In other words, putting ourselves in the shoes of someone in a difficult situation and seeing the situation from their perspective increases empathy and, consequently, helping.

Ways to help. The presence of other people in a help-seeking situation, the environment in which the help-seeking situation occurs, and the pressures of time constraints affect the way they help.

Altruism encompasses all human functions related to cognition and affect, values, feelings, goals, behavior and, in some cases, the consequences of behavior. Altruism is in human nature. Whether this structure is coded in genes, learned during the socialization process, or based on social norms, the result does not change. The typical individual feels the need to participate in welfare-related activities that benefit others or society as a whole. Forgiveness, help in emergencies or everyday situations, and altruism are manifestations of this need. The common feature of all altruistic behaviors is that they occur within the framework of the principle of voluntariness.

Thus, prosocial behavior, which is a form of social behavior, and altruism are mutually exclusive linking that prosocial behavior stems from altruism, as well prosocial as a motivation for altruism which causes behavior can be concluded. In the end, come to this conclusion that whether prosocial behavior or altruism the well-being of another although it is done for the sake of it, thoughts of personal gain are also manifested here.

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